

Tox24 Challenge¹

Igor V. Tetko^{1,2*}

¹Institute of Structural Biology, Molecular Targets and Therapeutics Center, Helmholtz Munich-Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Gesundheit und Umwelt (GmbH), DE-85764 Neuherberg, Germany

²BIGCHEM GmbH, Valerystr. 49, DE-85716 Unterschleißheim, Germany

The Tox24 challenge is designed to assess the progress in computational methods for predicting *in vitro* activity of compounds. The development of these methods has steadily gained momentum in the computational chemistry field since the groundbreaking Tox21 Challenge.¹ Since this time, significant advances have emerged in the field including new data,² harnessing novel modelling strategies and diverse applications,^{3,4} which encompasses an important topic addressed by the Chemical Research in Toxicology community of contributors and readers.

The chemicals and compounds being tested for activity against Transthyretin (TTR)⁵ within the "Toxicology in the 21st Century" (Tox21) initiative by the EPA² will be used as training and test sets for the upcoming Tox24 challenge. As was the case in the previous challenge, the goal of Tox24 is to "crowdsource" methods and approaches contributed by independent researchers in order to reveal how well they can predict compounds' interference in biochemical pathways using only chemical structure data. The computational models produced from the Challenge are expected to identify novel methods to be used for decision-making by environmental protection and health agencies, which can be used to determine which chemicals pose the greatest potential threat to human health. The Tox24 challenge is co-organised with the International Conference on Neural Networks (ICANN2024) conference and will run from mid May to the end of August 2024. The winner of the challenge will be announced during the ICANN2024 workshop "AI in Drug Discovery".⁶

The aim of this challenge will be to predict single concentration binding activities of compounds to TTR. TTR is one of the serum binding proteins responsible for delivering thyroid hormones to target tissues and maintaining the balance of free versus bound thyroid hormone (TH).⁷ The binding of compounds to TTR and subsequent displacement of TH is an important endpoint in the screening of chemicals for potential disruption of the thyroid system, within the wider objective of identifying endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs). Specifically, displacement of TH from TTR may result in reduced delivery of TH to target tissue and disruption of pathways dependent on TH activation.⁸ TH displaced from TTR may also be metabolised and excreted resulting in decreased serum TH levels.⁹ Due to the limited amount of data on binding activities of compounds to TTR, only a few computational studies are reported in the literature. For example Rybacka et al¹⁰ developed a classification model to predict TTR-binding (IC₅₀) measured at the 10 µM threshold using 203 compounds. In another study, molecular dynamics simulations based on crystallographic structures of human TTR with several thyroid hormone disrupting chemicals were used to predict 192 binders, out of which 12 representatives were subjected to *in vitro* testing.¹¹ Amid the tested compounds, seven compounds had binding affinities between 0.26 and 100 µM. A dataset of 136 compounds was measured by EPA for PFAS compounds.¹² The largest dataset with TTR binding

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activity included 444 compounds.⁹ While useful, such studies and datasets have limited value due to the low diversity of chemicals and/or collected data from different studies which may not be homogeneous. In the recent study⁵ a diverse set of 1512 chemicals was measured by the EPA, laying the foundation for the creation of models that can be applied to a much larger chemical space.

This dataset has been split into a training set (1012 compounds) as well as leaderboard set (200 compounds) and a blind set (300 compounds). The compounds from previous studies^{9,10,12} that overlapped with molecules in the challenge dataset were mainly used as part of the training set. It should be mentioned that some compounds are mixtures, while others are salts, and some contain metals. The structural information (SMILES) for data was originally retrieved from U.S. EPA's ToxCast libraries.² Several compounds in the original set did not have SMILES in ToxCast and so we retrieved missed structural information for them from PubChem based on CAS RN and names. Since the latter step could be error-prone, the challenge participants can search for more accurate structural representation of compounds to increase the accuracy of models. The activity data for the leaderboard set will be released to model developers on August 15th, and they can use these data to improve their models. The blind set data will be released after the end of the challenge (September 1st).

The winning model will be identified as the model providing the lowest RMSE between the predicted and calculated single point concentrations for the blind set compounds. In case of equal results (RMSE will be rounded to three digits) the first eligible final result to be submitted will be considered the winning contribution.

The winning team will be announced during the workshop and will be awarded a prize of 1,000€ to be sponsored by the challenge organisers. A winning team member will be invited to give a lecture during the AIDD workshop (in person or by Zoom). The winning team as well as other teams with RMSE not significantly different from that of the winning solution ($p > 0.05$ according to bootstrap¹³) will be invited to publish their studies or protocols in Chemical Research in Toxicology.

The data and other detailed submission guidelines for the challenge are announced on the website of the ICANN2024 conference <https://e-nns.org/icann2024/challenge>.

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